
Selected Primary Studies of Systematic Mapping

Table 25 presents the 45 studies selected in this systematic mapping, their ID, author name (s), publication title as an external link to where the study was published, and publication year.

Table 25 – List of included primary studies from the SoS developmento mapping

Source: Elaborated by the author.

Study ID	Included Study	Year
S0	Raymer (RAYMER, 1992)	1992
S1	Rossak et al. (ROSSAK <i>et al.</i> , 1994)	1994
S2	Ministry of Defence (PARTNERS, 2005)	2005
S3	Mostermanm et al. (MOSTERMANM <i>et al.</i> , 2005)	2005
S4	Boehm et al.(BOEHM; LANE, 2006)	2006
S5	Biltgen (BILTGEN, 2007)	2007
S6	Shams et al. (SHAMS <i>et al.</i> , 2008)	2008
S7	Gokhale et al. (GOKHALE <i>et al.</i> , 2008b)	2008
S8	Carbon et al. (CARBON <i>et al.</i> , 2008b)	2008
S9	Butterfield et al. (BUTTERFIELD <i>et al.</i> , 2008)	2008
S10	Reichle et al. (REICHLER <i>et al.</i> , 2008)	2008
S11	Kewley et al. (JR.; TOLK, 2009)	2009
S12	Ballagny et al. (BALLAGNY <i>et al.</i> , 2009)	2009
S13	Farcas et al. (FARCAS <i>et al.</i> , 2010)	2010
S14	Decher (DECHER, 2010b)	2010
S15	Calinescu et al. (CALINESCU; KWIATKOWSKA, 2008b)	2010
S16	Serugendo et al. (SERUGENDO <i>et al.</i> , 2010)	2010
S17	Department of Defense (OFFICER, 2010)	2010
S18	Tu et al. (TU <i>et al.</i> , 2011)	2011
S19	Farroha et al. (FARROHA; FARROHA, 2011b)	2011
S20	Dahmann et al. (DAHMANN <i>et al.</i> , 2011)	2011
S21	Mazzuchi et al. (MAZZUCHI; ALBAKRI, 2011)	2011
S22	Mensing et al. (MENSING <i>et al.</i> , 2012)	2012
S23	Li and Yang (LI; YANG, 2012)	2012
S24	Hallsteinsen et al. (HALLSTEINSEN <i>et al.</i> , 2012b)	2012
S25	Santamaria et al. (SANTAMARÍA <i>et al.</i> , 2012)	2012
S26	Ramos et al. (RAMOS <i>et al.</i> , 2012b)	2012
S27	Braga et al. (BRAGA <i>et al.</i> , 2012)	2012
S28	Taweel et al.(TAWEEL <i>et al.</i> , 2013)	2013
S29	Acheson et al. (ACHESON <i>et al.</i> , 2013)	2013
S30	Luna et al. (LUNA <i>et al.</i> , 2013a)	2013
S31	Madni and Sievers (MADNI; SIEVERS, 2014b)	2014
S32	Louali et al. (LOUALI <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	2014
S33	Sanduka et al. (SANDUKA; OBERMAISSER, 2014)	2014
S34	Ricci et al. (RICCI <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	2014
S35	Ergin et al. (KILICAY-ERGIN; DAGLI, 2015)	2015
S36	Barker and Summers (BARKER; SUMMERS, 2015)	2015
S37	Hu et al. (HU <i>et al.</i> , 2015)	2015
S38	Sharples (SHARPLES, 2015)	2015
S39	Diaz et al. (DIAZ <i>et al.</i> , 2016)	2016
S40	Naik (NAIK, 2016)	2016
S41	Raz et al. (RAZ <i>et al.</i> , 2016)	2016
S42	Sturdivant and Chong (STURDIVANT; CHONG, 2017)	2017
S43	Albers et al. (ALBERS <i>et al.</i> , 2018)	2018
S44	Loureiro et al. (LOUREIRO <i>et al.</i> , 2018)	2018
S45	Lu et al. (LU <i>et al.</i> , 2018)	2018